

D3.6

Guidelines for evaluation of proposals and for the selection of projects (JRP & JIP)

WP3 Joint Research Projects

Responsible Partner: Sciensano

Contributing partners: ANSES, BfR, RIVM, SVA, UCM, University of Surrey, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Guidelines for the evaluation of proposals and for the selection of projects (JRP & JIP)

General information on the OneHealth EJP is available on the website onehealthjep.eu.

For more insight in the [general procedure](#) for the submission of project proposals by candidate project leaders and the selection of the projects for funding, deliverable D3.3 should be consulted. The current document [details the evaluation process](#) of the project proposals by evaluators external to the OneHealth EJP consortium.

Contact details of the OneHealth EJP WP3 & WP4 teams and the Support Team

The Support Team may be contacted for general questions related to this procedure. More specific questions should be forwarded to the WP3 and WP4 teams, for research and integrative projects, respectively.

- OneHealth EJP Support Team: Arnaud Callegari, Lucyna Haaso-Bastin and Noémie Colinet, Email: ohjepcoord@anses.fr
- OneHealth EJP WP3 Team (Joint Research Projects): Hein Imberechts, Fanny Baudoin and Hendrik-Jan Roest, Email: ohjep@sciensano.be
- OneHealth EJP WP4 Team (Joint Integrative Projects): Ann Lindberg and Manuela Caniça, Email: ohjep-jip@sva.se

Role of the OneHealth WP3 & WP4 teams and the Support Team

Full proposals are submitted to the Support Team, and the WP3 and WP4 teams will administer the evaluation of the full proposals. Their role is:

- To check for completeness of the dossier and to keep an overview (e.g. priorities, budget, timing, etc.) of the project proposals;
- To contact external experts for the evaluation of the project proposals and to collect the evaluation forms;
- To transfer the evaluated proposals and accompanying documents (e.g. evaluation sheets) to the OneHealth EJP Coordinator and the Project Management Team.

Eligibility check of the full proposal

The WP3 and WP4 teams check the proposals for completeness, i.e. perform the eligibility check.

The EJP Coordinator may, after discussion with the Project Management Team, reject a proposal if it is judged incomplete. All other proposals will be sent to external experts for scientific evaluation. The candidate project leaders will be informed of the status of their proposal.

Identification of External Experts for Evaluation

The experts must not currently be engaged in or have had close collaboration with any of the OneHealth EJP partner organisations or individual participants in the past 5 years, i.e. as from January 2014 (see also further, Annex B).

To enhance the comparison of the outcome, all related proposals (i.e. submitted within a specific priority topic or a domain, or all JIP proposals) will be assessed by the same evaluators. More specifically, each evaluator may have to read up to 5 projects. Each proposal will be evaluated by at least three experts.

The WP3 and WP4 teams have identified experts by taking contact with organizers of former or ongoing European calls (EMIDA, ANIHWA, JPIAMR etc.), directly with academic experts from existing partner organizations networks and with some experts who collaborated in the evaluation of European projects under Societal Challenge Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry in 2017 and whose name are on the H2020 participant portal. The list of external experts and the detailed expertise will be stored and made available for future consultation, if requested.

Individual evaluation

The WP3 and WP4 teams will invite the experts to the evaluation process. The email will include:

- a short description of the OneHealth EJP with a link to the site web OneHealthEJP.eu
- copies of the following documents relevant for the assessment of the proposals:
 - ✓ the procedure for the submission and selection of project proposals, including the description of the selected priority topics for JRP and JIP;
 - ✓ this procedure for the evaluation of the proposals;
- the link to an online registration (“Registration as evaluator of full proposals (JRP & JIP) for OneHealth EJP”) allowing to notify the commitment of the possible evaluator, to specify her/his preference for one or more project topics as well as her/his agreement to act as a rapporteur (see further).

Before receiving the proposals for evaluation, the expert must agree on the terms as set out in the “Confidentiality Agreement” and “Protection of personal data (GDPR regulation)” (Annex A, form available on the OneHealth EJP website). **Duly signed agreements will have to be sent back to ohelj@sciensano.be**. A Sciensano collaborator will sign the agreement and mail it back to the expert.

The expert who accepts the confidentiality and data protection agreement-will receive digital copies of the following documents:

- the project proposal(s);
- the comments that the Project Management Team made on the candidate’s Letter of Intent, i.e. remarks revealed before the candidate project leaders sent in the full proposal;
- a confirmation of “No Conflict of Interest” (Annex B, form available on the OneHealth EJP website): based on the identity of the consortium members mentioned in the proposal abstract, each expert should first assess her/his possible conflict of Interest with the project proposal;
- a template to mark the evaluation scores and comments (Annex C, form available on the OneHealth EJP website).

Each expert will have to send a scanned copy of the signed “No Conflict of Interest” document (Annex B) to ohelj@sciensano.be prior to evaluating the proposal. In case of a conflict of interest, the external expert is excluded from the evaluation process and she/he will be asked to destroy the project proposal.

Criteria for evaluation

For the proposal evaluation, the following criteria will have to be assessed according to the scoring scheme below. The criteria for both the Joint Research Projects (JRP) or Integrative Project (JIP) are:

- Ability to align with call text objectives: How well does the proposal adhere to the objectives listed in the topic description?
- Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach: Does the project propose a sound and scientifically qualified concept that promises progress beyond the state-of-the-art? Are the objectives realistic, are the scientific and technological methodologies and the work plan convincing? Is a multi-disciplinary approach stimulated?
- Quality and efficiency of the implementation: Projects should be assessed for the coherence and effectiveness of their work plan, including appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources; complementarity of the participants within the consortium; appropriateness of the management structures and procedures, including risk and innovation management. Also the effectiveness of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the project results, to communicate the project, and to manage research data where relevant should be evaluated.
- Integration:
 - **For JRP**: Does the project contain relevant integrative activities (i.e. capacity building, development of harmonised protocols, joint strains and biobank collections, joint databases, harmonised surveillance strategies, addressing legal aspects of general interest) that will allow partner organisations to improve harmonization or alignment in order to better support their prevent-detect-response tasks within the scope of the project topic?
 - **For JIP**: Will the project aim at the cooperation and collaboration of a larger group of organizations and member states in the consortium to attain the general objective of the OneHealth EJP, i.e. to improve preparedness and prevent-detect-response? Will additional organizations be able to join at a later stage?
- Sustainability: Will any developments within the project be maintained within the organisations in the consortium (procedures as well as infrastructure)? Will the impact of the project last over a long period of time or is it likely to generate a more limited effect? Is the project outcome likely to have positive secondary effects such as a positive impact on the economy (free travel over borders, trade of animals and food, recall of contaminated food stuffs etc.) or the environment (impact of preventive and mitigating measures, reduce transportation, etc.)?

The external evaluator will assess the proposal as follows:

1. scoring all criteria giving whole numbers from 0 to 5; this will allow a distinct ranking with a maximum score of 25; an aid to fill in the evaluation form is provided in Annex D, form available on [the OneHealth EJP website](#);
2. commenting on each criterion in a few lines; this will help to give feedback to both the candidate project leaders and the Scientific Steering Board that will select the projects.

The duly filled in evaluation forms (Annex C) have to be sent back to oejp@sciensano.be. In order to evenly spread the work over the available evaluation period, the reports are expected according to the following scheme, assuming reading 5 proposals:

- A first report in the first week,
- The second and third report in the second and third week, and
- The fourth and fifth report in the last week of the four weeks evaluation period.

In that sense, work is evenly spread over the entire evaluation period

The general scoring scheme for the criteria is as follows:

0	Weak	The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. The criterion under examination is not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor	The proposal addresses the criterion unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.
2	Good	The proposal broadly addresses the criterion; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.
3	Very good	The proposal addresses most of the criterion well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.
4	Excellent	The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to that criterion. It contains no significant elements to be improved.
5	Outstanding	The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to this criterion. It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion in question. Any shortcomings are minor.

In Annex D these general descriptions are turned into a [practical scoring guide](#) with quality definitions for each of the five criteria at each level. This grid should help evaluators assigning consistent scorings.

Reading panel

The individual reports of the experts form the basis of the further evaluation. In so-called consensus groups experts who have evaluated the same proposal will join during a tele- or videoconference to agree on a consensus on the quality and eventually on the ranking of the proposals. The WP3 and WP4 teams will set up these meetings in the period May-June 2019.

In each consensus group the rappporteur will seek consensus in the quality evaluation and the ranking. The rapporteur is impartial and has to ensure that each proposal is evaluated fairly according to the evaluation criteria.

Selection of the projects (JRP & JIP)

The conclusion of the consensus group is presented to the Scientific Steering Board in September 2019, who will select the projects for funding. The projects are due to start in January 2020.

Annexes

Annex A

Part 1. Confidentiality Agreement

OneHealth EJP proposal documents as well as documents such as mails, letters, etc regarding the evaluation of the proposals are confidential and should therefore be handled and stored with due care and confidentiality.

Experts are therefore not allowed to disclose any information concerning proposal documents or evaluations to outsiders, nor are they allowed to use this confidential information to their own benefit or anyone else's benefit or disadvantage. In addition, they may not reveal to outsiders (including the partners of project proposals) that they are assessing the research plan of a particular researcher. Anyone who has questions about the proposal documents or evaluation reports shall be advised to contact ohjep@sciensano.be.

Once the evaluation has been completed, experts are requested to destroy all proposal documents and any copies made of them. Confidentiality must also be maintained for three (3) years after the evaluation process has been completed.

Part 2. Protection of personal data (GDPR regulation)

Information concerning the protection of the expert's personal data

The One Health European Joint Programme organises the online registration of evaluators at Sciensano, Brussels, ("Registration as evaluator of full proposals (JRP & JIP) for OneHealth EJP") to identify international experts in the field of the One Health EJP's second call and to facilitate their assignment to a reading panel that will evaluate scientific project proposals.

The online tool collects personal data of candidate experts and includes questions on their availability, their preferences regarding the priority topics to be evaluated and their willingness to be rapporteur.

If the expert agrees to participate in the evaluation process, he/she needs to sign the consent form.

Objective of the registration tool

The aim of this online tool ("Registration as evaluator of full proposals (JRP & JIP) for OneHealth EJP") is to facilitate the assignment of international experts to a reading panel of reviewers. Its outcome will only be used for this particular purpose.

Reimbursement

If the expert decides to review OneHealth EJP proposals, he/she will be reimbursed a fee of €450 euros for 4 proposals (i.e. the actual fee for experts working for the EC, which equals reimbursement for 1 working day). The actual fee to be paid will be calculated pro rata the number of proposals read, i.e. €562.5 in case of reading 5 proposals.

In case the expert decides to be rapporteur for that panel, he/she will get an additional fee of €225.

Confidentiality

The expert's data will be stored for use by Sciensano. The expert's identity who has participated in the evaluation of project proposals may also appear in official OneHealth EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC and become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project. This process is conducted in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation of May 25, 2018. The expert can access he/she collected data at any time.

Concerning the protection of the expert's personal data

The information requested will be used in accordance to the permission the expert has given to the Belgian law of 30 July 2018 concerning the protection of individuals in relation to the use of personalized data and the European regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and the Council of 27 April 2016 (in place since 25 May 2018) concerning the protection of people in relation to the use of personalized data and the free flow of data (GDPR).

If the expert decides to fill in his/her personalized data in the online tool, he/she confirms to have gone through these privacy conditions.

Which personal data Sciensano collects in the online registration tool?

- The expert's first name and family name
- The organisation for which the expert works
- The country where the expert works
- The expert's professional e-mail
- The expert's availability to be a reviewer
- The expert's preferences regarding the priority topics to be evaluated
- The expert's willingness to act as a rapporteur

Who collects the expert's data?

Sciensano is responsible for the collection of the data.

How do we collect the expert's personal data?

Through the online registration tool.

Sharing the expert's data

The expert's data will be shared with Ann Lindberg (SVA, SE), Manuela Caniça (INSA, PT) and Arnaud Callegari (ANSES, FR) who support and supervise the evaluation process of project proposals (joint research and joint integrative projects, see www.OneHealthEJP.eu for details). The expert's identity who has participated in the evaluation of project proposals may also appear in official OneHealth EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC and eventually become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project.

Saving and protecting the expert's personal data

The expert's data will be saved in electronic form (LymeSurvey, csv table).

Sciensano will save the expert's personal data until the end of the OneHealth EJP project, i.e. until December 2022.

The expert's choice regarding his/her personal data

The expert has the right to ask Sciensano whether his/her data were used. To do this, the expert will have to write a formal request in which is specified what he/she wants to know, rectify or delete. This request has to be dated, signed and accompanied by a copy recto-verso of the expert's ID-card, together with contacting details. If the expert's data are indeed used, he/she has the right to ask for access to the data Sciensano has and may ask for the period in which the data were saved and used. The expert can also ask to rectify and delete the data, she/he can oppose the use of the data or limit the use of the data. If the data has to be deleted, the question has to be motivated. If the conditions are fulfilled, Sciensano will in the shortest delays honour the request and inform the expert about it.

How can the expert contact us?

For questions regarding the use of personal data by Sciensano in the framework of the OneHealth EJP tool, the expert can contact us:

Sciensano

Juliette Wytsmanstraat 14
1050 Elsene
Belgium
T. : +32 2 642 51 11
F. : +32 2 642 50 01
info@sciensano.be
www.sciensano.be

The Sciensano service Data Protection and the Officer for Data Protection can be contacted by email at dpo@sciensano.be.

The expert also has the right to file a complaint about how his/her data have been handled to the Belgian supervising authorities responsible for the legal aspects regarding the protection of personal data. This service can be contacted at:

Data protection authority

Rue de la Presse 35
1000 Brussels
BelgiumT. : + 32 (0)2 274 48 00
F. : +32 (0)2 274 48 35
contact@apd-gba.be
www.dataprotectionauthority.be

Additional information

Additional information about this study can be obtained from the scientific OHEJP coordinator via email (othejp@sciensano.be) or telephone (+32 474 989 843).

Consent Form

I agree with the Confidentiality Agreement regarding the content of the project proposal

Yes No

I have read, understood and approved the information form regarding the protection of my personal data. I have had enough time to think and I have been able to ask all the questions that have come to mind. I understand that if I have more questions or concerns about the use of my personal data, I can contact Sciensano (details mentioned above).

Yes No

I understand that my online registration (“Registration as evaluator of full proposals (JRP & JIP) for OneHealth EJP”) is voluntary and that by signing the form I will commit to reading and assessing the project proposals (up to five).

Yes No

I agree with the regulations concerning the protection of personal data as explained above, the fact that my personal data as expert who has participated in the evaluation of project proposals will be used by Sciensano and that my identity may also appear in official OneHealth EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC and eventually become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project.

Yes No

Name of expert:

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohelp@sciensano.be

To be completed by Sciensano’s collaborators Hein Imberechts or Fanny Baudoin, for OneHealth EJP

I informed the external expert / evaluator about the content of the online registration tool and the confidentiality of the data collection. I have answered all the questions raised about this survey.

Name and first name:

Date

Signature

Annex B – Confirmation of No Conflict of Interest

External Experts are requested to declare any actual or potential conflict of interest towards the proposals. Disqualification may be essential for a number of reasons:

- If the expert:
 - was involved in the preparation of any proposal submitted for this second call under the OneHealth EJP;
 - is a director, trustee or partner or is in any way involved in the management of the proposal;
 - is employed or contracted by one of the beneficiaries;
 - has close family ties or other close personal relationship with the project leader or deputy leader of the proposal;
 - has (or has had during the last five years) a scientific collaboration with the project leader or deputy leader of the proposal;
 - has (or has had) a relationship of scientific rivalry or professional hostility with the project leader or deputy leader of the proposal;
 - has (or has had), a mentor/mentee relationship with the project leader or deputy leader of the proposal;
- If the approval or rejection of the proposal may in any way benefit or harm the expert personally.

Disqualification will also be inevitable if their impartiality may otherwise be endangered, or if they feel that they have a conflict of interest.

In case of a possible conflict of interest the person must notify ohelj@sciensano.be without any delay.

I hereby confirm that I do not have a conflict of interest.

Name of expert:

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohelj@sciensano.be

Annex C - Template for the evaluation of joint research and integrative project proposals

Please consult Annex D for a practical scoring guide with quality definitions for each of the five criteria at each level.

- Indicate: Foodborne zoonoses Antimicrobial resistance
 Emerging threats Integrative project

Project title or acronym:

	0 Weak	1 Poor	2 Good	3 Very good	4 Excel- lent	5 Out- standing
Ability to align with call text objectives						
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach						
Quality and efficiency of the implementation						
Integration						
Sustainability						

Total score (max 25):

Remarks (please include at least one comment per criterion)

Ability to align with call text objectives:

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Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach:

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Quality and efficiency of the implementation:

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Integration:

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Sustainability:

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Please do not sign or indicate your name. Send a scan of the duly filled in document to: ohelp@sciensano.be.

Annex D – Guidance for scoring of research and integrative projects

	0 - Weak	1 - Poor	2 - Good	3 - Very good	4 - Excellent	5 - Outstanding
Ability to align with call text objectives : How well does the proposal adhere to the objectives listed in the topic description?	The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. The call text objectives are not addressed or the alignment with the call text objectives cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.	The proposal addresses the call text objectives unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.	The proposal broadly addresses the call text objectives ; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.	The proposal addresses most of the call text objectives well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.	The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to the call text objectives . It contains no significant elements to be improved.	The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to the call text objectives . It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the call text objectives. Any shortcomings are minor.
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach : Does the project propose a sound and scientifically qualified concept that promises progress beyond the state-of-the-art? Are the objectives realistic, are the scientific and technological methodologies and the work plan convincing? Is a multi-disciplinary approach stimulated?	The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. The scientific excellence and/or innovative approach cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.	The proposal meets the goal of scientific excellence and/or innovative approach unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.	The proposal broadly addresses the goal of scientific excellence and/or innovative approach ; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.	The proposal addresses most of the goal for scientific excellence and/or innovative approach well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.	The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to the goal for scientific excellence and/or innovative approach . It contains no significant elements to be improved.	The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to the goal for scientific excellence and/or innovative approach . It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of scientific excellence and/or innovative approach . Any shortcomings are minor.

	0 - Weak	1 - Poor	2 - Good	3 - Very good	4 - Excellent	5 - Outstanding
<p>Quality and efficiency of the implementation: Projects should be assessed for the coherence and effectiveness of their work plan, including appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources; complementarity of the participants within the consortium; appropriateness of the management structures and procedures, including risk and innovation management. Also the effectiveness of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the project results, to communicate the project, and to manage research data where relevant should be evaluated.</p>	<p>The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. The quality and efficiency of the implementation cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.</p>	<p>The proposal meets the goal of high quality and efficient implementation unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.</p>	<p>The proposal broadly addresses the goal for high quality and efficient implementation; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses most of the goal for high quality and efficient implementation well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to the goal for high quality and efficient implementation. It contains no significant elements to be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to the goal for high quality and efficient implementation. It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of high quality and efficient implementation. Any shortcomings are minor.</p>
<p>Integration JRP: Does the project contain relevant integrative activities (i.e. capacity building, development of protocols, strains and biobank collections, databases, surveillance strategies, legal aspects) that will allow partner organisations to improve harmonization or alignment in order to better support their prevent-detect-response tasks within the scope of the project topic?</p>	<p>The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. The integrative activities are not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses integrative activities unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.</p>	<p>The proposal broadly addresses integrative activities; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses integrative activities well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to integrative activities. It contains no significant elements to be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to integrative activities. It successfully addresses all relevant aspects integrative activities. Any shortcomings are minor.</p>

	0 - Weak	1 - Poor	2 - Good	3 - Very good	4 - Excellent	5 - Outstanding
<p>Integration JIP: Will the project aim at the cooperation and collaboration of a larger group of organizations and member states to attain the general objective of the OneHealth EJP, i.e. to improve preparedness and prevent-detect-response? Will additional organizations be able to join at a later stage?</p>	<p>The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. The integrative goals are not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses the integrative goals unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.</p>	<p>The proposal broadly addresses the integrative goals; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses most of the integrative goals well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to the integrative goals. It contains no significant elements to be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to the integrative goals. It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the integrative goals. Any shortcomings are minor.</p>
<p>Sustainability: Will any developments within the project be maintained within the organisations in the consortium (procedures as well as infrastructure)? Will the impact of the project last over a long period of time or is it likely to generate a more limited effect? Is the project outcome likely to have positive secondary effects such as a positive impact on the economy (free travel over borders, trade of animals and food, recall of contaminated food stuffs etc.) or the environment (impact of preventive and mitigating measures, reduce transportation, etc.)?</p>	<p>The proposal shows severe flaws that are detrimental to the proposed project. Sustainability aspirations are not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses its sustainability aspirations unsatisfactorily or in an inadequate manner. It shows serious weaknesses, resulting in the need of substantial modification or improvement.</p>	<p>The proposal broadly addresses its sustainability aspirations; however, it contains some weaknesses and elements that can be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal addresses most of its sustainability aspirations well; however, it contains a few elements that could be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal is of high quality and internationally competitive related to its sustainability aspirations. It contains no significant elements to be improved.</p>	<p>The proposal stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation and progress of science at a global level related to its sustainability aspirations. It successfully addresses all relevant aspects of sustainability aspirations. Any shortcomings are minor.</p>